

Printed Chip Interconnects for MicroLED Displays

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Abstract

This paper presents a newly developed process for interconnecting microICs with microLEDs through ultra-precise dispensing of conductive silver-based ink. Special cleaning and surface energy modification processes have been introduced to achieve interconnects with a width of 5 μm and a minimum pitch of 20 μm . The developed technology is part of the EU funded project “Building Active matrix MicroLED displays By Additive Manufacturing” (BAMBAM) which develops unique manufacturing technologies for realizing microLED displays without TFT backplanes.

Keywords

Additive Manufacturing; Micro Printing; microIC; microLED

1. Introduction

The BAMBAM project's objective is to use additive manufacturing processes to develop a microLED display for fine pitch video wall segments without using a TFT backplane [1]. Therefore, the final process has a lower energy demand in production compared to LCD or OLED displays due to the lack of a TFT backplane and its high energy demands during manufacturing. The basic concept is to place microICs and microLEDs on a polyimide-based PCB with single pixel structures via mass transfer and to interconnect these components with a silver-based nanoparticle ink through printing [2].

This paper presents the process to realize these printed interconnections on $95 \times 55 \times 10 \mu\text{m}^3$ microICs with a pad size of $5 \times 5 \mu\text{m}^2$ in combination with a $750 \times 600 \times 100 \mu\text{m}^3$ R&D microLED on glass. Especially the process of the microIC interconnects regarding substrate preparation and printing will be discussed. Because the final BAMBAM pixel is based on a microPackage concept, the presented process is also adapted to a 25 μm thin polyimide PCB which is used to produce digital pixels for a 40×40 pixel active matrix demonstrator [2]. Additionally, the successful light up of interconnected pixels on glass is demonstrated.

2. Ultra-Precise Deposition (UPD) Process

The XTPL Delta printing system is able to deposit various types of conductive and non-conductive materials through glass nozzles. Depending on the material, the nozzle must be in contact or at most a few micrometers above the substrate. The used CL85 ink in this work is a silver nanoparticle-based ink with a viscosity above 10^5 cP. The minimum nozzle size for this ink can be down to 1.5 μm in diameter [4]. Material deposition is reached by a pressure to the nozzle which can be set up to 10 bar. Due to its non-Newtonian nature the effective viscosity of the paste at the tip is reduced under velocity such that a printing process becomes possible [5]. The dispensed Ag nanoparticle ink must be sintered to reach the final conductivity. Usually for maximum conductivity this is done in the oven at $250^\circ\text{C}/20$ min. In this work a nozzle with a diameter of 5 μm is used build in the printer with a tilt angle of 50° . The printing pressure was dynamically optimized for a printing speed of 50 $\mu\text{m}/\text{s}$ at an acceleration and deceleration of 20 mm/s^2 . To define the printing routine, XTPL's

proprietary scripting language is used. To print an interconnection on such small pad sizes it is especially important to take the dynamics of the ink into account. Due to the ink's high viscosity there is a delay after application of the pressure until ink flows and touches the surface. This delay time must pass before starting the nozzle movement.

3. Surface Preparation for Printed MicroIC Interconnects

This chapter describes the experiments used to achieve microIC interconnects on glass and the process transfer to polyimide. The experiments divide into substrate cleaning and surface energy modification before printing and SEM investigation of the printed structure.

3.1. Experiments on Glass

Usually printing on flat surfaces is possible without any surface preparation. Interconnecting discrete chips brings also a third spatial dimension which changes ink behavior especially when having interfaces of different materials. The mass transfer of microICs for the BAMBAM project is done by micro-transfer printing which uses an epoxy on the target substrate that is removed by plasma etching after transfer [3]. Without any preparation effort of the substrate, the Ag wire printing result is not able to reach the requirements for a functional chip interconnect (Figure 1). This means that neither a non-cracking line nor a short-circuit-free connection can be guaranteed.

Figure 1: Printed microIC interconnections without substrate preparation

Applying hot DI water cleaning procedure with ultrasonic agitation was found to effectively clean the surface after plasma removal of the epoxy layer. This yields major improvement in printing quality. Because of the small pitch between the interconnects and high capillary forces, the printed ink was spreading along the chip edges. This behavior caused short-circuits between the printed lines (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Printed microIC interconnections after substrate cleaning, shorted at the chip edges

To prevent these shorts, various processes for surface energy modification have been investigated. Using photoresist to fill the capillaries was successful to prevent the ink from spreading along the edges. Fluorinating with SF₆ Plasma improved the printed structure on the substrate but not on the Si₃N₄ edges of the chips, so the ink still spread at these edges. However, surface energy modification by applying a self-assembling monolayer (SAM) yielded the best results regarding short circuit free printing, resolution and crack free interconnects. This approach solves the ink spreading issue and makes it possible to additionally apply more ink for better edge coverage due to higher contact angle of the ink on the monolayer (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Interconnected microIC on glass after modifying the surface energy with SAM

To create a monolayer with these properties different compositions with Trichlorosilane anchor groups are suitable. For the interconnects on glass such a layer yielded the best results. This is most likely because of an increase of the contact angle (Figure 4) of the Triethylenglycol based ink to the substrate due to the fluor content in the head groups of the used silane. The material can be evaporated in a vacuum chamber at 90°C and is stable for the sintering parameters of the ink. Trichlorosilane as the anchor group of the monolayer does not adhere on metals which guarantees electrical conductivity at the contact pads such that this process is self-aligned.

Figure 4: Triethylenglycol (10 μl) on glass a) without SAM b) with SAM

Using this process for glass substrates, a 4x4 Pixel Demonstrator with blue R&D microLEDs was produced (Figure 5 and Figure 6). This demonstrator serves to verify the processes developed up to this point, such as: mass transfer of microICs, Ag wire printing and testing of the used FPGA driving.

Figure 5: Blue microLED interconnected with microICs by UPD printing process with SAM

The light up of the 4x4 demonstrator showed that the introduced process is able to realize working printed interconnections between microLEDs and microICs. The interconnecting process for the microIC was verified for three substrates on all printed devices.

Figure 6: Light up of the 4x4 blue pixel demonstrator

3.2. Process Transfer to Polyimide PCB Substrates

For the final BAMBAM microPackaged pixel the microIC's outputs are interconnected to three singulated microLEDs with a size of $70 \times 30 \mu\text{m}^2$ on a polyimide PCB foil. To test this process before the availability of the final microLED, all outputs have been shorted to VDD (Figure 8). This allows the measurement of the electrical functionality via the total current drawn from VDD.

The direct transfer of the monolayer process to the BAMBAM microPackage was not possible (Figure 7). It is clearly visible that the monolayer is still functional which is indicated by the non-spreading ink at the chip edges. However, a significant amount of the printed interconnects cracked after sintering at the top edge of the micro IC thus interrupting the electrical connection. Noticeable in Figure 7 is that the interconnects on the right side do not show this issue. This was also the case for other samples with the same surface preparation process.

Figure 7: Interconnected microIC on $25 \mu\text{m}$ thick polyimide PCB after using SAM process

On the SEM picture in Figure 7 and more clearly in Figure 8 it is visible that the epoxy used for microIC bonding is not fully etched around the printed chip. This is because the epoxy is spin coated which leads to a thicker layer close to the $7 \mu\text{m}$ high copper structures of the microPackage PCB that is not fully etched by the process used for the microIC transfer. Therefore, a difference in ink adhesion and thermal expansion may be the reason why the ink is cracking on the left side of the micro IC in Figure 7.

Figure 8: Printed microIC with epoxy residues close to copper structure on a polyimide PCB

Introducing an additional surface treatment step before applying the SAM to remove the epoxy around the chip was able to solve this behavior (Figure 9 and Figure 10). Using reactive ion etching (RIE) with O_2 , Ar and CF_4 turned out to be the most effective process to remove the epoxy and prepare the surface for the monolayer deposition (Figure 9). A higher magnification image of the printed interconnects as in Figure 10 shows that this process is now able to reach the requirements of $5 \mu\text{m}$ wide lines on chip pads with a minimum pitch of $20 \mu\text{m}$

Figure 9: MicroIC interconnections on the BAMBAM polyimide PCB microPackage after plasma treatment and SAM

The substrate surrounding the chip in Figure 9 shows that after RIE treatment the epoxy is fully removed. Therefore, the surface is pure polyimide with the SAM on top which was already functional on the chip side without epoxy residues.

Figure 10: Printed microIC interconnections on a $25 \mu\text{m}$ thick polyimide PCB without cracks and shorts

To eliminate the need of removing material by RIE further surface treatment steps for the BAMBAM polyimide microPackage have been investigated. Using different SAM materials did not yield crack free interconnects as neither did surface energy modification by SF_6 plasma. The only method to remove the need of an etching step turned out to be UV-Ozone cleaning right before the monolayer evaporation. This approach finally yielded crack free interconnects also on top of the not removed epoxy (Figure 11).

Figure 11: MicroIC interconnects after UV-Ozone and SAM treatment without removing epoxy surrounding the chip

It is therefore reasonable to assume that the effect of the applied monolayer was negatively influenced by organic residues on the epoxy surface.

4. Results and Discussion

The experiments in surface treatment before printing and sintering yielded several findings. When printing over steps the Ag nanoparticle ink is at risk of spreading and forming cracks. The spreading of the ink is caused by capillary forces which can be reduced with proper surface energy variation by introducing a SAM that generates a more hydrophobic surface. The quality of this monolayer depends on the material where it is deposited and its surface. Because of this, the adhesion of the ink may differ according to the monolayer quality. Therefore, the occurrence of cracks is most likely because of different adhesion strength across the printed surface which is then causing cracks while sintering. The best results were achieved when having a similar adhesion on all material interfaces. In this work this was achieved by removing or modifying an epoxy layer that is used to mount chips before applying a monolayer that introduce the same surface adhesion over the whole printing path.

Manufacturing single RGB pixel on a thin polyimide PCB foil with a complex topology becomes now possible with this process. As the key approach of the BAMBAM project, this microPackaged pixel will be transferred by pick and place to a simple PCB backplane for a microLED display demonstrator with 40x40 pixel.

5. Conclusion

This work proves the concept of using a printing technology to realize chip interconnects that can be used to manufacture a microLED display without using a TFT backplane. Necessary processes to achieve ultra-precise printed interconnects of driver chips and microLEDs have been developed. This yields to a possible display manufacturing solution that can be much more sustainable as no high energy demanding thin film transistor technology is used.

6. Acknowledgements

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